

DANCING

Resource List

Projects, Toolkits, and Resources
related to Cultural Participation of
Persons with Disabilities

Protecting the Right to Culture of Persons with Disabilities
and Enhancing Cultural Diversity through European Union
Law: Exploring New Paths (DANCING)

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Introduction¹

1.1 The DANCING Project in a Nutshell

The project 'Protecting the Right to Culture of Persons with Disabilities and Enhancing Cultural Diversity through European Union Law: Exploring New Paths (DANCING)' explores the right of persons with disabilities to take part in cultural life as an essential aspect of enhancing cultural diversity in the European Union (EU). The project is funded by the European Research Council (ERC) and is based at Maynooth University (MU), Ireland under Professor Delia Ferri as a Principal Investigator (PI). It explores the extent to which the protection of the right to take part in culture of people with disabilities and the promotion of cultural diversity intersect and complement each other in the EU legal order. On the whole, DANCING deploys interdisciplinary approaches to produce ground-breaking knowledge intended to challenge the cultural exclusion often faced by people with disabilities, contributing to the creation of a more inclusive and culturally diverse European society.

DANCING commenced on 1 September 2020 and is due to be completed on 31 August 2025. It comprises four Work Packages (WPs). Within WP1, DANCING has identified and categorised barriers to and facilitators of cultural participation experienced by persons with disabilities and how they affect the wider cultural domain (experiential objective). Within WP2, DANCING has provided a normative exploration of how the EU has used and can use its competence to combat discrimination and its supporting competence on cultural

matters, in synergy with its wide internal market powers, to ensure the accessibility of cultural activities, to promote disability identities, while achieving cultural diversity (normative objective). WP3 has aimed at advancing the understanding of the legal concept of cultural diversity, which stems from the intersection of different sources of law, and, in the final phase of the project, articulates a new theorisation of the promotion of cultural diversity within the EU legal order (theoretical objective). The project is underpinned by the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), which represents the global legal standard on disability rights, and is informed by the human rights model of disability.

DANCING also includes a fourth cross-cutting WP (WP4) focused on raising awareness, deploying specific outputs for the general public and producing a number of toolkits and guidelines that aim to advance the understanding of what facilitates cultural participation of people with disabilities, legal change and effective policy responses at the EU level. As part of this WP, as will be discussed in the following subsection, we compiled this Resource List which provides information on existing organisations, projects, outputs and good practices related to culture and disability in a broad fashion, or that concern cultural participation of persons with disabilities.

1.2 Aim of the Resource List

This Resource List aims to highlight projects, initiatives, toolkits and reports that have a focus on cultural participation by and involving persons with disabilities, the accessibility of cultural content, and the overall relation between disability and the Cultural and Creative Sectors (CCS). In doing so, this Resource List includes references to existing tools and resources which may be of interest to organisations of persons with disabilities (OPDs), cultural organisations, as well as academics, policymakers and civil society organisations.

This Resource List **does not provide a systematic quantitative review**, but instead includes a list of **selected** projects and tools carried out/produced in Europe, many of which have been supported by EU funding. It is important to note that this **List is not exhaustive** and does not provide a comprehensive appraisal.

The idea of this Resource List arises from findings of WP1, which highlighted that there is still a piecemeal approach to cultural participation of persons with disabilities with many obstacles to ensuring their inclusion and the accessibility of cultural content and venues. As argued in other academic outputs of the

DANCING project, good practices in relation to accessibility and inclusion are fragmented and often confined within the specific and limited timeframes of projects.¹ A recurring theme among participants in the empirical research of the DANCING project was the 'loss' of good practices. This happens either because such good practices are linked to a project, with a specific timeframe and funding, and are discontinued after the end of a given project, or because such good practices rely on the distinct expertise of certain employees, artists or cultural workers, and discontinue following the exit or retirement of such an expert. Interview responses frequently indicated that, despite the publication of numerous guides and checklists promoting good practices across different countries, cultural organisations still face challenges in their proper use and implementation. Moreover, the adoption of a systematic approach to embed accessibility and inclusive practices into the CCS and into mainstream cultural activities seems still very slow. This is engendered by the tendency for cultural funding not to include specific accessibility budget lines, or, even when they do, such funding is allocated for bespoke (often short-term) projects rather than for sustained, long-term actions aimed at integrating accessibility

into all cultural goods and services. For example, a participant of the DANCING research observed that although many innovative projects and ideas for increasing accessibility exist, accessibility rarely becomes mainstream.² Hence this Resource List aims to support and stimulate mutual learning to avoid fragmentation of efforts and the engendering of existing piecemeal approaches.

1.3 Approach to the Resource List

The DANCING project compiled a non-exhaustive sample of existing initiatives promoting the cultural participation of people with disabilities, to serve as a repository and a **resource for those working in cultural organisations wanting to know more about initiatives and projects**, and to **facilitate connections** among different initiatives and hopefully **foster future collaborative efforts**.

This Resource List includes transnational and national initiatives, funded by the EU or by national or sub-national/local authorities, or by private sponsors, which either started or were ongoing between the 1 January 2010 (the year of the EU ratification of the CRPD, and one of the main starting points of focus adopted by the DANCING project), and 31 December 2024.

1 Leahy, A. and Ferri, D. (2023b). Barriers to Cultural Participation by People with Disabilities in Europe: a Study Across 28 Countries, *Disability and Society*, 39(10), 2465–2487. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2023.2222898>

2 Ferri, D., Leahy, A., Šubic, N., & Urzel, L. (2022). Implementing the right of people with disabilities to participate in cultural life across five European Countries: Narratives and counter-narratives, *Journal of Human Rights Practice*, 14(3), 859–878. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhuman/huac035>

This Resource List was mainly put together through desk-based research, with a focus on selected funding streams, and on taking into account inputs from participants in the qualitative research of the project and well as inputs from a selected range of reviewers. The desk-based research that informed the Resource List entailed a search conducted on several databases using keywords relevant for the project. More specifically, for EU funded projects, the research started from the European Commission website of [Creative Europe](#). In the 'Projects' section which lists the programmes funded by Creative Europe, we typed in the specific keyword: 'disab*' which enabled us to efficiently find all the projects mentioning the relevant umbrella terms 'disability', 'disabilities', 'disabled' all at once. Then, the description or abstract of each project was examined to assess their relevance in relation to the DANCING objectives and in light of the findings of WP1. In addition to the Creative Europe website, the projects in this List are also drawn from the [CORDIS](#) website which presents Research and Development projects funded by EU Research programmes as well as the [Erasmus+](#) website with EU funded projects centred around social inclusion, the green and digital transitions, and promoting young people's participation in democratic life. While the same approach was used on CORDIS and Erasmus+, due to different settings and filters, research results were much broader

which led to a more in-depth screening of identified projects. We therefore used the following keywords where appropriate: 'disab*'/ 'access'/'inclusion' as well as any of the search terms 'arts', 'cultur*', 'museum', 'galler*', 'heritage'. We also undertook a more general scoping exercise investigating activities and initiatives carried out by organisations leading or collaborating with the projects already retrieved.

The research focused mainly on results provided by English keywords and while some resources are in the national language of the initiative, particular emphasis is placed on English sources, or sources with translations available as we wish for the content to be accessible to an EU-wide audience as far as possible. With regards to projects deployed at the national or local level, and funded through state funding or other sources of funding, we aimed to include at least one national initiative from each EU Member State and from the UK. As noted above some initiatives had been mentioned by participants in our qualitative research. We then investigated whether organisations leading or collaborating with identified EU-funded projects had led nationally-funded initiatives on cultural participation of people with disabilities. We searched on websites of national cultural agencies and councils, and we engaged in a residual search through Google using different combinations of the terms 'disability', 'accessibility', 'art', 'culture'. Here again, we conducted a thorough

screening to select initiatives that align with DANCING's focus and objectives or that produced relevant toolkits, guides and materials. For the list of national initiatives, we identified a variety of toolkits - such as guides, reports, training materials, and policies - and other outputs (such as artistic outputs or performances).

This Resource List does not aim to be exhaustive. We largely limit ourselves to listing projects with a primary focus on disability and culture, with particular emphasis on those which produced outputs and toolkits that might be used by other cultural organisations for future initiatives and to improve accessibility and inclusion. Further, DANCING as a project and the authors of this Resource List are not responsible for the content of resources listed or for the projects listed. Any feedback on the resources listed should be addressed directly to the organisations that published them. The resources and links provided to third-party websites, articles, tools, or content are for informational purposes only. We do not endorse, guarantee, or take responsibility for the accuracy, reliability, or completeness of any information, products, services, or content found on external websites.

In line with the CRPD, DANCING uses 'people first language' (i.e. persons/ people with disabilities).³ This is consistent with the approach applied throughout the project and in the various outputs, communications and activities, including in reports. However, it is im-

³ In line with the European Union of the Deaf and other organisations, DANCING uses the term 'Deaf people/persons' but acknowledge that this term is not used by everyone, nor is it wording which everyone identifies with or agrees with.

portant to note that the resources mentioned in this List use terminology which corresponds to each initiative's core values and messaging. These terms may not necessarily reflect the language used in DANCING, however interpretations can vary across countries, cultures, legal frameworks, and linguistic contexts explaining these variations, especially considering the wide scope covered by this Resource List.

1.4 Scope of the Resource List

As noted above, in line with the European scope of the project, this Resource List focuses mainly on projects and tools funded through EU funding programmes, with particular attention to the [Creative Europe programme](#), as well as a small number of projects funded under other EU programmes such as [Erasmus+](#) and [Horizon 2020](#). In all cases these projects involve a strong emphasis on arts, culture and disability, accessibility, inclusion for persons with disabilities, and/or Deaf culture, even when that is not their sole focus. The Creative Europe programme is the most important cultural funding tool operating at EU level. The programme comprises three strands, namely the Culture Strand, the Media and the Cross-sectoral Strands. The Culture Strand, which is of key relevance here, aims to enhance cooperation and exchanges among cultural organisations and artists in areas such as cultural heritage, literature and publishing, music, or performing arts, to increase access to and partic-

ipation in culture as well as social inclusion through culture. Creative Europe supports a wide range of CCS, working in Europe and beyond.

EU funding of CCS, such as the cultural funding programme Creative Europe, greatly support the cultural participation of persons with disabilities and could even facilitate the advancement of the implementation of [Article 30 CRPD](#). Additionally, more and more cross-sectoral initiatives intersect with and enhance EU cultural policies while advancing the cultural participation of persons with disabilities. Another notable measure of support from the EU on the matter of access to cultural life for people with disabilities is the [Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030 \(Strategy 2021–2030\)](#), which lays down the current EU disability policy framework, and sets out that an accessible and inclusive culture is 'essential for full participation in society' of persons with disabilities. All these EU initiatives acknowledge the growing need to improve access to cultural rights for all, including people with disabilities.

1.5 Structure of the Resource List

The structure of this Resource List is as follows. Section 2 comprises EU-funded projects as retrieved in line with our search strategy set out above. The primary focus is on EU-funded projects and the List is divided into sub-sections on performing arts focused projects, GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Mu-

seums) and Heritage Sites related projects, and other projects, respectively.

Section 3 includes projects carried out at national level, and funded by national or private fundings. This section tackles both initiatives from each EU Member States, as well as examples for the UK.

2 Selected EU-funded projects

The following list of EU funded projects is divided by art-form. We first list projects and initiatives related to performing arts. Then, projects and initiatives related to GLAM and heritage sectors are laid out before listing some other projects. The List also includes

the type/stream of funding. In particular, we present them by type of funding and by the year in which they commenced, listing the projects that started most recently first, and including links to some of their relevant outputs.

2.1 Performing Arts

Funding	Project Title and Time Frame	Project Website or Funder Website	Project Coordinator	Countries Covered by the Project	Project Description	Outputs/Toolkits/Useful Resources created by the Project
Creative Europe	Europe Beyond Access (01/01/2024 – 31/12/2027)	European Commission (EC) website	SKANES DANSTEATER AB (Sweden)	Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain and Sweden.	Focus on the active participation of artists with disabilities in mainstream dance and theatre through transnational creation and institutional learning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Toolkit Resources. Different types of resources such as reports, directories, and training guides advancing the cultural participation of persons with disabilities both as artists and audiences. ▪ ‘Learning Journey’ for Funders and Policymakers. Series of resources aimed at cultural policymakers and arts funders to make the arts more diverse and accessible. ▪ ADICLUS Position Paper. State of the art analysis and recommendations by the European Arts and Disability Cluster (ADICLUS), developing professional opportunities for cultural professionals with disabilities.

Creative Europe	Let's PASS (01/01/2024 – 31/01/2026)	Project Website	FONDAZIONE ARTURO TOS-CANINI (Italy)	Italy, Finland, Greece, and Czechia.	Focus on accessibility, engagement, and visibility for individuals with cognitive and sensory disabilities in the performing arts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Workshops: Visual Artistic Residencies. A two hour creative exploration, online, open to people with or without disabilities cultivating a common ground of practices, group discussions and reflections through movement.
Creative Europe	NEW REV - Reveland - transforming arts into immersive and inclusive experiences (01/03/2023 – 30/06/2025)	EC Website	STICHTING POSSIBILIZE (the Netherlands)	Belgium, Bulgaria, France, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, and Spain.	Aim of making live music performances more accessible and interesting for people with disabilities, without separating them from the rest of the audience through immersive sensory effects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Glossary: Inclusion in Live Music the Right Words to Build it. An interactive glossary developed to help anyone who wants to find a more appropriate, non-offensive and inclusive way to talk about disabilities. ▪ Creative Accessibility Workshop. A workshop enabling organisations to become more aware of the possibilities of creative accessibility.
Creative Europe	AAA - All Areas Access - A Mock-up for Accessible Venues (01/02/2023 – 31/07/2024)	EC Website	AUSGANG S.R.L. (Italy)	Belgium, Italy, and Portugal.	Focus on the study, test and dissemination of good practices aimed at improving accessibility to non-institutional live venues for Deaf people.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All Areas Access Guidelines. Guidelines for more accessible venues for Deaf audiences. ▪ All Areas Access: A survey with Deaf audience. Results of a survey with Deaf audiences of concerts considering types of services that would improve accessibility.

Creative Europe	T.O.U.C.H. - Theatre Outreach: Unravelling Connections in Humans (01/07/2022 - 30/06/2024)	EC Website	CENTAR ZA POZITIVAN RAZVOJ DECE I OMLADINE. (Serbia)	Serbia, Croatia and Italy.	Innovation in the field of audience development and social inclusion through culture and art. (Culture Strand).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource Page. Various reports, training modules and handbooks on theatre.
Creative Europe	Crossing the Line / Trasna Na Líne (01/09/2019 – 15/02/2023)	EC Website	STIFTELSEN MOOMSTEATERN. (Sweden)	France, Sweden, Ireland, Poland, and the Netherlands.	Collaboration of professional theatre companies working with artists with disabilities to work and learn together by sharing creative working processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination material. Various dissemination materials such as videos, leaflets, summaries and more. ▪ Trasna Na Líne, a European partnership project, 2019 – 2023. Report of Crossing the Line project with reflections and learnings.
Creative Europe	Power - Performances of Wide Enrichment to Raise awareness on different abilities and promote integration (01/09/2018 - 31/12/2021)	EC Website	NAZARENO SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA SOCIALE. (Italy)	Czechia, Greece, Ireland, and Italy.	Promotion of the transnational co-production of a theatre play with actors with disabilities to enhance the skills and knowledge of operators that usually organise artistic activities for people with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Workshops. Various workshops dedicated to artists and organisations to promote accessibility and inclusion.
Creative Europe	Audience Blending by Arts Europe (ABbA) (01/07/2017 - 31/12/2019)	EC Website	GEMEENSCHAPSCENTRUM DE ZEYP (Belgium)	Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, Portugal, and the UK.	Aim of bringing Deaf and hearing communities together in bilingual theatre with blended audiences and, both sign languages and spoken languages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated Bilingual Theatre by Practice A Guide to Producing Theatre in Sign and Spoken Language. Guide including artistic and technical recommendations towards the inclusive bilingual theatre format.

Creative Europe	Moving Beyond Inclusion (Dance) (01/07/2016 - 29/06/2018)	EC Website	CANDOCO DANCE COMPANY (UK)	Croatia, Germany, Italy, Sweden, and the UK.	Creative exchange to improve skills and expertise for the professional inclusive sector of dance artists both with and without disabilities via peer network sharing and choreographic research sessions and labs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Moving Beyond Inclusion: An Artistic Resource. Collection of interviews and conversations with dance artists both with and without disabilities who have engaged with the activities of the project.
Creative Europe	Un-Label - New Grounds for inclusive Performing Arts (01/05/2015 - 31/10/2017)	EC Website	VEREIN DER FREUNDE UND FORDERER DES SOMMERTHEATER PUSTEBLUME E.V. (Germany)	Germany, Greece, Türkiye, and the UK.	Collaboration of emerging professional performers with and without disabilities supported by a group of experienced cultural workers to develop together a series of workshops and seminars.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovation Diversity – New Approaches of Cultural Encounter In Europe, (2017). Manual including a section on best practices, practical guidelines and a list of professional companies and cultural organisations working in the field of inclusive performing arts across European countries.
Creative Europe through the Perform Europe funding scheme	Breaking the Hamster Wheel – from Effort to Impact: better strategies for increasing the accessibility of touring youth theatre (2024-2025)	Perform Europe Website	Not Applicable (N.A.)	Germany, Luxembourg and Liechtenstein.	Collaboration to develop better professional practices for accessibility in touring theatre long-term and to develop formats to reduce the barriers experienced by certain audiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ‘HAMSTERRAD’ piece of contemporary theatre. (In German) Access-augmented performances of ‘HAMSTERRAD’ at the centre of the project.

Creative Europe through the Perform Europe funding scheme	Dancing with Excess (2024-2025)	Perform Europe Website	N.A.	Germany, Italy, Slovakia, and North Macedonia.	Focus on disability activism, identity, and innovative choreography, by involving presentations of dance duet 'Skin' between dancers with and without disabilities and workshops for people of different ages and abilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 'SKIN' dance duet performance. Theme of multiple lived experiences co-existing. The two apparently disparate performers find common movement languages that question the usual ideas of choreography between both dancers with and without disability.
Creative Europe through the Perform Europe funding scheme	Diversity Typical – Embracing Neurodiversity through Movement (2024-2025)	Perform Europe Website	N.A.	Malta, Romania, and Italy.	Contemporary dance tour, integrating performance campaigns and workshops on themes of inclusion and tolerance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diversely Typical Dance Performance. Dance piece that has been choreographed to highlight behavioural nuance of certain neurological diversity and to stop the stigma against neurodiversity.
Creative Europe through the Perform Europe funding scheme	SYN.Tropia dance concert for Deaf people and other hearings. (2024-2025)	Perform Europe Website	N.A.	Portugal, Greece, Lithuania, and Latvia.	Dance-concert crafted by established Portuguese artist duo, to engage both Deaf and hearing audiences, and disseminate sonic content through touch, followed by a discussion, and workshops.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ SYN. Tropia Dance Concert. (In Portuguese) Use of unprecedented device called a 'Tactile Listening Board', available both for Deaf and hearing audiences, which disseminates sonic content through touch.

Creative Europe through the Perform Europe funding scheme	Wounds of the colonial past – Healing together for a shared future (2024-2025)	Perform Europe Website	N.A.	Czechia, Germany, and France.	Touring of a performance which deals with the intergenerational wounds and traumas of colonisation in an inclusive setting for Deaf artists and audiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Šrámy/ la débattue, site-specific research combining circus, physical theatre and visual/video art. The partnership pursues an intersectional approach to address diversity and inclusion through the medium of circus.
Erasmus+	Access and Aesthetic (01/09/2019 – 31/07/2022)	EC Website	HEADWAY ARTS (UK)	England, Finland, Portugal, and Sweden.	Exploration of inclusive practice in the arts to improve the access, opportunities and experience of neurodiverse people or people with disabilities in cultural life that allow total access for all audience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Video documentary. Resource for artists and facilitators, in the form of a video documentary exploring promising practices and techniques to use within the arts & disability sector.
Erasmus+	Yes We Are In (01/11/2018 – 31/10/2021)	EC Website	GEMEENSCHAPSCENTRUM DE ZEYP (Belgium)	Belgium, Croatia, Finland, and the UK.	Collaboration of theatre groups with adult actors with intellectual disabilities who want to experiment in the digital world, to make an artistic journey, and to discover intercultural Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes We Are In Livestream Handbook. Toolkit on the activities led in the project, the methodology used and provision of guidelines to inclusive livestreaming for a broad audience including a list of barriers generally encountered by people with disabilities in relation to live streaming.

Erasmus+	Creative Inclusion in Adult Education (C.I.A.E.) (01/11/2017 – 31/10/2019)	EC Website	COPE FOUNDATION (Ireland)	Belgium, France, Ireland, and Italy.	Aim of improving opportunities for adult learners with disabilities, engaging with arts education and leading to further diversity and opportunity in the workplace.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Guidelines: Creative Inclusion in Adult Education (C.I.A.E.). Tools on inclusive art and education.
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2.2 GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) and Heritage Sites

Funding	Project Title and Time Frame	Project Website or Funder Website	Project Coordinator	Countries Covered by the Project	Project Description	Outputs/Toolkits/Useful Resources created by the Project
Creative Europe	BEAM UP: Blind Engagement in Accessible Museum Projects (01/10/2020 – 30/09/2023)	EC Website	COOPERATIVA ATLANTE SOCIETA COOPERATIVA (Italy)	Ireland, Italy, and Croatia.	Improvement of services for visually impaired people in museums by collaborating with visually impaired people in the field of contemporary art. The project involved museum professionals and blind and visual disability experts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Beam Flashbook. Practical & reusable resources for the practitioners, containing all the main elements of the project such as methodology, case studies and information on findings.
Creative Europe	VIBE, Voyage Inside a Blind Experience (01/06/2017 – 31/08/2019)	EC Website	COOPERATIVA ATLANTE SOCIETA COOPERATIVA (Italy)	Ireland, Italy, and Croatia.	VIBE, a project that preceded BEAM UP sought to create the first model of a contemporary art exhibition accessible both to sighted and visually impaired people.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Vibe Flashbook. Practical & reusable resources for the practitioners, containing all the main elements of the project and the description of the different phases of its implementation.

HORIZON 2020	MuseIT, Multi-sensory, User-centred, Shared cultural Experiences through Interactive Technologies (01/10/2022 – 30/09/2025)	EC Website	HOEGSKOLAN I BORAS (Sweden)	Cyprus, Greece, Sweden, Belgium, France, Italy, and the Netherlands.	Focus on designing cutting-edge technologies to facilitate, promote and widen access to cultural assets in an inclusive way by developing a multisensory, user-centred platform for remote immersive co-creative engagement with cultural assets and experiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Outputs and Deliverables. Links to public deliverables and publications of the project.
HORIZON 2020	ARCHES - Accessible Resources for Cultural Heritage EcoSystems (01/10/2016 - 31/12/2019)	EC Website	VRVIS ZENTRUM FÜR VIRTUAL REALITY UND VISUALISIERUNG FORSCHUNGSGMBH (Austria)	UK, Austria, Spain, and Serbia.	Focus on the accessibility of museums and cultural heritage through models and technologies, and principally for those experiencing disabilities of perception, memory, cognition and communication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ways of working with ARCHES participants Guidelines. Guidelines and other documents available for use in cultural institutions developed through the framework of the ARCHES project.

2.3 Other Projects

Funding	Project Title and Time Frame	Project Website or Funder Website	Project Coordinator	Countries Covered by the Project	Project Description	Outputs/Toolkits/Useful Resources created by the Project
Creative Europe	One World International Human Rights Documentary Film Festival (06/07/2016 – 06/07/2017)	EC Website	CLOVEK V TISNI OPS (Czechia)	Czechia.	Initiative called 'One World for All', aimed at all audiences with disabilities, and aiming to attract visitors with disabilities implemented for the first time at a Czech film festival. (Media Strand)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Festival priorities. Highlights notable aspect of the festival such as immersive films, sustainability, the use of sensitive and inclusive language and more.

Creative Europe	Quantum Music (01/08/2015 – 31/05/2018)	EC Website	INSTITUTE OF MUSICOLOGY OF SERBIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES AND ARTS (Serbia)	Denmark, Serbia, and Slovenia.	Aim of exploring the connection between music and quantum physics through the creation of a new art and science experiments for live performance. (Culture Strand).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Literature. Writings and publications of the project.
Employment and Social Innovation "EaSI"	The Art of Inclusion Conference (14-15/10/2020)	ENCC Website	EASPD (European Association of Service Providers for Persons with Disabilities); ENCC (European Network of Cultural Centres); COPE FOUNDATION	N.A.	Collaboration of advocates, experts, policymakers, thinkers and practitioners to discuss how cooperation between the cultural sector, artists with disabilities and disability service providers can create new inclusive opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conference Report. Programme and summary of the panels presented.
European Regional Development Fund – Interreg Central Europe	CE-Spaces4All (01/03/2023-28/02/2026)	Interreg Website	GEODETIC INSTITUTE OF SLOVENIA (Slovenia)	Slovenia, Croatia, Hungary, Austria, Czechia, and Poland.	Collaboration of public authorities, the tourism sector and people with disabilities to improve governance for more accessible tourism.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Trainings on accessible tourism. Focus on accessible events preparation, raising awareness of the European Accessibility Act or good practices in accessible tourism, and more.
Directorate-General Employment, Social Affairs of the European Commission	AccessibleEU Centre	EC Website	FUNDACIÓN ONCE (Spain)	EU wide and online.	Resource centre on accessibility to ensure the participation of persons with disabilities in all areas of life on an equal basis with others.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Guidelines and support material. Guidelines for implementing accessibility in places, products and services, providing knowledge about accessibility legislation, regulation and standards.

3 Selected national initiatives

Our research conducted under WP1 has unveiled an array of useful resources and good practices of cultural organisations that implement accessibility for persons with disabilities, as well as projects and initiatives in all EU Member States and in the UK. Often, as part of these initiatives, project toolkits, outputs or reports that aim to be of practical use to organisations and professionals operating in the cultural field wishing to be more

inclusive or to work more with people with disabilities and/or Deaf people, are funded by national or private funding. We do not attempt to provide a complete listing of organisations providing such outputs, which are considerable in number and in different languages. Instead, we include a sample, designed to illustrate a variety of good practices that can support cross-fertilisation, exchange and the advancement of the role of

people with disabilities in cultural life overall. The List is presented in alphabetical order of the country in which the organisation is based.

Several of the organisations listed, to which links are provided, offer further lists of published resources and outputs that may act as resources, so we encourage readers to engage with them.

Funding	Project Title and Time Frame	Project Organisation or Funder Website	Countries of the Project	Project Description	Outputs/Toolkits/Useful Resources created by the Project
Essl Foundation MGE gemeinnützige Privatstiftung	Zero Project	Organisation Website	Austria	Aim of finding and sharing solutions that improve the daily lives and legal rights of all persons with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Zero Project Inclusive Arts. The initiative is dedicated to highlighting the transformative power of Arts and Culture and to sharing solutions to remove barriers faced by people with disabilities in cultural settings.
Austrian Federal Ministry of Arts, Culture, Civil Service and Sport	The Belvedere	Organisation Website	Austria	One of the world’s leading museums focused on exhibiting, researching, collecting, communicating, and preserving.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accessibility Page. List of all existing measures to ensure accessibility, as well as guiding principles.
Francophones Bruxelles; Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles; Actiris Brussels	La Concertation (Action Culturelle Bruxelloise)	Organisation Website	Belgium	Regional collaborations aiming to strengthen cultural rights and represent the reality of Brussels for all.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Parcours Diversite. (In French) Issues to consider when implementing solutions aimed at accessibility and inclusion in culture.

Flemish Government	VisitFlanders	Organisation Website	Belgium	Tourism website ensuring inclusion for everyone: visitors of all ages and tourists with or without disabilities when planning a trip to Flanders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accessibility Finder. Research tools enabling tourists with disabilities to look for accessible accommodations and activities to do and their specific accessibility measures.
Bulgarian Ministry of Culture	Touch the Gallery	Organisation Website	Bulgaria	Museum which preserves, studies and enriches the national collection of Bulgarian and foreign art for present and future generations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Touch the Gallery Exhibition. Exhibition for visitors with visual impairment using tactile maps and audio descriptions.
City of Zagreb and the City Office for Culture of the City of Zagreb	Trešnjevska Cultural Centre	Organisation Website	Croatia	Modern institution working on a variety of cultural programmes for all age groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2nd UPSET ART Festival of Arts and Inclusion of People with Disabilities (2020). Presentation of talents and skills of people with disabilities, recognising their creative contribution in society, culture and the arts as equal to others.
Government of Croatia	E-citizens	Organisation Website	Croatia	National Service Portal of Information for various public services.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Repertory. (In Croatian) List of institutions with adapted and/or specialised programmes for persons with disabilities, and of Institutions and associations funded or co-funded by the Ministry of Culture and Media.
Ministry of Education and Culture in collaboration with Cyprus Chamber of Fine Arts	Neofytos Cultural (Disability) Organization	Organisation Website	Cyprus	Aim of fighting the social exclusion that many people with disabilities experience in cultural spaces.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dis Group Art Exhibition. Contemporary works of art that will develop critical thinking and raise awareness through disability.

Ministry of Culture of Czechia; and various Czech media partners.	GHMP Prague City Gallery	Organisation Website	Czechia	Collaboration between disciplines as a new and inspirational way of sharing messages with a broader audience and reducing the social exclusion lived by people with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Art interactively for visitors with special needs. Tours for visitors with disabilities, activities for visitors with mental illnesses, tactile activities for sight-impaired visitors, and overall events for people of various communities and minorities. All art activities are properly adapted for each particular group.
Billedkunstneres Forbund; Dreyers Fond; Roskilde Festival Fonden; Bevica Fonden; Bikubenfonden; and Statens Kunstfond	Mapping Disability Access to Danish Art Spaces	Project Website	Denmark	Aim to use creative perspectives to collectively address issues of cultural barriers and to map out what access currently means in Danish art spaces.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Self-reported cultural access maps. Digital resource bank where users can explore the limited space that art workers with disabilities must operate in and display the liveable area and access to the art field for an individual living with specific access needs.
City of Tallinn	TERATEATER theatre of blind and visually impaired people in Estonia	Organisation website	Estonia	Promotion of accessibility in the performing arts in Estonia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Festival. (In Estonian) Features discussion groups, performances of four different productions, workshops, photo exhibitions and a festival club.
Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture	Culture for All - Kulttuurikaikille	Organisation Website	Finland	Aim of improving the possibilities for financially hard-pressed young people, adults and families to participate in the cultural life and to do art as a hobby.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publications on "Accessibility" and "Diversity". Outputs such as accessibility and diversity checklists for museums, event coordinators, and accessibility guides for cinemas. ▪ Projects in the area of accessibility and disability. Culture for All Service coordinates projects in the area of accessibility and diversity.
French Government; French Ministry of Culture	European Centre for Cultural Accessibility (CEMAFORRE)	Organisation Website	France	Aim to develop and promote access to culture for all, and especially for people with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cemaforre Written Outputs. (In French) Several outputs in the field of access to culture for people with disabilities.

French Ministry of Culture; Universcience	Meeting of Cultural Establishments for Accessibility (RECA)	Organisation Website	France	Collaboration of public establishments to improve the reception of people with disabilities in cultural venues, by reflecting within various working groups and developing concrete inter-institutional actions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2024 Practical Guide of Cultural Outings. (In French) Guide bringing together all the concrete information essential for the preparation of cultural outings and projects in an accessible way.
French Ministry of Culture; French Ministry of Work, Health and Solidarity; Regional and City Funding; Various National Disability Foundations and Arts Foundations and Organisations.	Culture Relax/ Cinemadifference	Organisation Website	France	Support of cultural organisations in their accessibility policies to improve the inclusion of people with disabilities and/or neurodiversity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Training workshops. (In French) Modules to bring awareness on diversity, disability and accessibility for the staff of cultural organisations.
Berlin Funding: Berlin Sustainability Programme Inclusion 23	Kompagnie Tanzfähig (DanceCapable)	Organisation Website	Germany	Building of an inclusive dance company to develop the opportunity for further training in inclusive dance movement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Milestones. (In German) Following the milestones of the project, their initiatives, updates and best practices.
PS-Art e.V. Berlin	Galerie ART CRU Berlin	Organisation Website	Germany	Non-profit gallery which presents artworks by artists with mental disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exhibitions. (In German) List of exhibitions and projects held by the gallery in reversed chronological order.
General Secretariat for Youth; Ministry of Culture; Ministry of Labour; and other foundations.	ArtTogether	Organisation Website	Greece	Promotion of the rights of people with disabilities in art expression and creation as well as their equal access to cultural life.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cultural Programmes. (In Greek) Two important programmes of access to culture: The guided tours of groups with disabilities in museums, archaeological and other cultural sites; and the audio description of theatrical and other performances for visually impaired people.

Hungarian Equal Opportunity Programme	Hungarian National Gallery	Organisation Website	Hungary	Opportunities to diversely showcase the work of artists often belonging to marginalised communities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exhibition. Event presenting the works of artists with and without disabilities.
The Arts Council of Ireland/An Chomhairle Ealaíon	Arts & Disability Ireland	Organisation Website	Ireland	National resource organisation for arts and disability, promoting art at all levels, as professional artists, audience members with disabilities of all kinds and ensuring accessibility of venues.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Media Centre, publications. A library retracing the various strategy and policy reports on arts and disability through the years as well as special edition reports on the best practices of notable accessible performances.
National and Regional Funding; Arts Organisations and Disability Organisations	Arts for All Ireland	Organisation Website	Ireland	Group of stakeholders interested in arts and inclusion and supporting Cork City and region to become a “European Centre of Excellence for Inclusive Arts”.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Arts for All Charter Booklet. Public commitment to diversity and inclusion. By signing this charter, arts organisations and cultural institutes will commit to building on their inclusion and diversity strategy. ▪ Disability Training Outputs. Conversations on arts practitioners and the inclusion and highlighting of minorities within the world of the arts.
Brothers of Charity Services; Private funds	That’s Life	Organisation Website	Ireland	Arts and personal development program for people with intellectual disability to participate in through a wide range of high quality arts programs run by established creative artists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Video archive. Depository of behind the scenes videos showcasing the project’s highlights.
Ministry of Culture – Directorate-General for Entertainment	Oriente Occidente	Organisation Website	Italy	Promotion of the development of networks of relationships through the language of dance to overcome boundaries of language, ethnicity, gender, age, culture.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rifrazioni. Two accessible live performance of dancers with disabilities, with workshops, actions of approach and accessibility for the public and communication actions attentive to the different needs of the audiences.

Ministry of Culture; Veneto Region; Municipality of Verona; Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Crafts and Agriculture of Verona	Fondazione Arena di Verona/ Arena Opera Festival	Organisation Website	Italy	Aim to perform non-profit cultural activities of public utility, pursuing the dissemination of musical art and musical education for the general public.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ‘Arena per Tutti (Arena for All)’. Even more accessible Arena di Verona Opera Festival with Multisensory paths to discover the backstage, accessible trailers and theatre books, cards in easy-to-read language and 1,500 more seats reserved for people with sensory and intellectual disabilities.
Autonomous Province of Trento	Mart Museum, Museum of Modern and Contemporary Art of Trento and Rovereto	Organisation Website	Italy	Conceived as a cultural hub rather than a traditional museum, Mart represents a true ‘contemporary landscape’.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accessibility Page and commitments. (Partly in Italian) Videos on the inclusivity of the museum as well as commitment to abide by including a video on Information in Sign Language and an Augmentative and Alternative Communication guide.
Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Tourism - General Directorate for Museums	A.D. Arte – L’Informazione. Un Sistema informativo per la qualità della fruizione di beni culturali da parte di persone con esigenze specifiche	Project Website	Italy	Providing verified information on the real conditions of accessibility of state museums and archaeological areas open to the public for all those who want to approach Italy’s cultural heritage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ List of the accessible Italian cultural sites. The list goes into great details on the existing accessibility feature of each site.

De Agostini Foundation- <i>L'Abilità</i> Onlus Association	Museo per tutti – Accessibile alle persone con disabilità intellettiva	Project Website	Italy	Museo per tutti is developed in several actions conducted by a working group composed of experts in cultural heritage and accessibility, starting from the peculiarities of each of the participating museums, an innovative training and participatory planning path is created for museum staff to build a guide usable by people with intellectual disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ List of museums. The project provides accessible materials (Easy to Read, CAA etc.) about the museums for visitors with disabilities to prepare their visits ahead of time.
Funds change each year but usually mainly Latvian national and regional funds as well as funds from other curators' countries.	Latvian Centre for Contemporary Art (LCCA)	Organisation Website	Latvia	Promotion of the development of contemporary art processes in Latvia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Survival Kit Festival. Annual festival with the mission to critically investigate and reflect on the evolution of contemporary society and highlighting the importance of accessibility, and assisting people with disabilities.
Public Benefit National Funds	Foundation "Come Along!" / Fonds Nāc līdzās!	Organisation Website	Latvia	Various cultural activities serve as the main tool to support and enhance children and young people with disabilities' inclusion into society.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Finished Projects. List showcasing all the major milestones and achievements of the organisation.
Lithuanian Council for Culture	Museum of Occupations and Freedom Struggles	Organisation Website	Lithuania	Museum aiming to collect, preserve, research and promote historical-documentary material reflecting Lithuanian history.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exhibitions "In the shoes of Lithuanian partisans...". (In Lithuanian) An exhibition of sensations for blind and visually impaired people through a presentation of stories in a sensory way (olfactory, hearing, touch are included).

National Cultural Fund (FOCUNA)	Kulturpass - Cultur 'All	Organisation Website	Luxembourg	Sensitise partners as well as public authorities on the importance of the right and access to culture, so that resources are available to all.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Kulturpass. Enables people with modest income to participate in Luxembourg's cultural life with a free card providing cheap if not free access to cultural opportunities. ▪ 2022 Report: Yearly report of progress as well as the following year's goal.
Arts Council of Malta through the Cultural Partnerships Agreement, and Premju tal- President għall-Kreattivitàta'	Opening Doors	Organisation Website	Malta	Opportunities for adults with intellectual disabilities through weekly arts training and yearly performances.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Annual Reports. Report on the activities and achievements of the previous year.
Arts Council of Malta	Arts Council of Malta	Organisation Website	Malta	Investment in the arts to strengthen Malta's creative and cultural landscape.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Right to Culture resource pack. Initiative aimed at increasing awareness regarding inclusivity and supporting the implementation of cultural rights.
Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences	Strengthening inclusive collaboration within the theatre (Versterking van inclusieve samenwerking binnen het theatre)	Project Website	The Netherlands	Collaboration between cultural organisations and universities to gain knowledge about inclusivity in theatre and make it widely accessible.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Experiments outputs. (In Dutch) Interviews, videos, and written guides on the accessibility of art obtained through over 50 interviews led by the project.
Fonds Voor Cultur Participatie; Performing Arts Fund Netherlands; Den Haag funding	Holland Dance Festival	Organisation Website	The Netherlands	Dance Festival hosting inclusive wide range of educational activities, special projects, workshops, and ongoing, tailor-made programmes for groups of all backgrounds, generations, and social classes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DanceAble Workshops. Classes where dancers with and without disabilities are welcome to join together, either independently or with their personal assistant. ▪ Education. Creation of custom-made educational dance programmes.

Amsterdam University of Arts, Thematic Cooperation Programme (TCP)	Academy of Theatre and Dance: Arts Beyond Ableism	Organisation Website	The Netherlands	Group of ten art educators and researchers gathered to share their experiences in inclusive work practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Arts Beyond Ableism Conference: Art, Education, and Social Justice. Focus on unlearning ableism in the arts: how artists and educators can help counter biases against people with disabilities in art, education, and society.
City of Poznan	ZAMEK Culture Centre in Poznań	Organisation Website	Poland	Development of the most interesting cultural phenomena through visual arts, theatre, film, music and literature.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cinema Without Barriers Festival. (In Polish) Initiative that connects the world of film and accessibility, while promoting equality in access to film culture.
M.st. Warsaw	Theatre 21 Foundation	Organisation Website	Poland	Theatre group whose actors are mainly people with Down syndrome and autism.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Calendar. (In Polish) List of upcoming plays all disclosing accessibility measures put in place to reach a broader audience.
Caixa Geral de Depósitos	Culturgest	Organisation Website	Portugal	Dedicated to contemporary creation and presenting a regular programme of performing arts, music, visual arts, cinema and contemporary thought aimed at a diverse public.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accessibility page. The organisation details their measures to ensure accessibility for people with disabilities.
BPI e da Fundação “la Caixa”. Arts Council Portugal	Acceso Cultura	Organisation Website	Portugal	Cultural professionals and people interested in accessibility issues in general, namely physical, social and intellectual.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publications. (In Portuguese) Various guidelines to promote and improve the accessibility of cultural events to people with disabilities.

British Council Romania, Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands, Timisoara Project Centre, Ideilagram Association, AMAIS, Roman Catholic Archdiocese of Bucharest, Accessible Romania by Sano Touring and the Zâmbreanu family	Superheroes Among Us	Organisation Website	Romania	Promotion of the social inclusion of people with disabilities through accessible cultural events by offering consultancy in adapting concerts, plays, exhibitions and other types of cultural activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Olga's Movies. (In Romanian) Film screenings adapted for people with disabilities. Here, all neurodiverse people and people with different disabilities are welcome within an accessible and inclusive cinema hall.
Ministry of Tourism and Sports of Slovakia	Visit Bratislava	Organisation Website	Slovakia	Official national tourist information centre for Bratislava.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accessible Bratislava Map. List assessing the accessibility of Bratislava's biggest cultural monuments.
Slovenian Tourist Board	I Feel Slovenia	Organisation Website	Slovenia	Official national tourist information centre for Slovenia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accessible Tourism. Resource page listing inclusive and accessible cultural sights of Slovenia.
Spanish Government; Red.Es; Kit Digitl; Fund of Recuperation and Resilience	Teatro Accesible	Organisation Website	Spain	Dedication to integrating accessibility measures into theatre in Spain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Training on accessibility and inclusion in the performing arts. (In Spanish) Reports on accessibility in theatres and in performing arts as well as 1 minute recap videos on accessibility.

Västra Götaland Region; Region Jönköping County; Region Skåne and Jönköping Municipality; Foundation Signatur	ShareMusic & Performing Arts	Organisation Website	Sweden	Swedish national knowledge centre for artistic development and inclusion working for everyone's right to experience, participate in and practice artistic and cultural activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The Inclusive Co-Creative Ensemble. Starting point for realising inclusive work within music. The book can be used as an advisor, a toolkit, springboard to ensure inclusive artistic work reflecting the approach used at ShareMusic & Performing Arts.
Municipality of Skåne	Skåne Dansteater Dance Company (member of Svensk Scenkonst, Swedish Performing Arts Association)	Organisation Website	Sweden	Dance workshops, lectures, seminars, talks and tours and collaborate with dancers with and without disabilities, with professionals and non-professionals.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IDance Workshop. Specially tailored for participants with disabilities. ▪ Relaxed Performance. Performance for anyone who prefers or needs a more flexible and relaxed performance experience, specifically people with disabilities.
KulturKadet; Skåne and other Swedish funders	Moomsteatern	Organisation Website	Sweden	An inclusive theatre with groundbreaking actors with learning disabilities, based in Sweden.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Archive. Repertory of past performances focused on a diverse and inclusive group of artists and performers in an accessible environment.
Swedish Government	Swedish Agency for Participation	Organisation Website	Sweden	Promotion of implementation of disability policy by developing and spreading information about obstacles to participation, and supporting public-sector bodies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Guidelines for associations. (In Swedish) Inspiration and concrete tips on what associations can do to enable more people to have an active leisure time.
Swedish Inheritance Fund	Dance Variation (run by Studieförbundet Vuxenskolan)	Organisation Website	Sweden	Inclusive dancing and leadership for people with intellectual disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Booklet. (In Swedish) Over a 100 inclusive dance exercises. ▪ Dance exercise. (In Swedish) Videos and documentations about inclusive dance exercises performed.

British Council Arts	Disability Arts International	Organisation Website	UK	Aim of promoting the work artists with disabilities and inclusive arts organisations working on increasing access to the arts for people with disabilities, as audiences, visitors and performers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Newsletter. Shares exclusive content about artists with disabilities and inclusive companies making innovative change in regards to accessibility and inclusion.
Paul Hamlyn Foundation - Arts Council England	Disability Arts Online	Organisation Website	UK	Led by people with disabilities to support artists and arts audiences with disabilities to enable social change.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resources -Disability Arts Online. Guides, Toolkits, and Webinars; but also Research and Learning material to gain practical advice about accessibility and professional development for organisations and artists; as well as to gain knowledge and insights from academics, artists, writers and arts organisations directly.
Arts Council England; Farnham maltings; Disability Confident Employer	StopGap Inclusive Dance Company	Organisation Website	UK	Leading and advocating for disability access in dancing and advancing inclusivity and best practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource Page. List of Resource on Inclusive Choreography with Webinars, Guides, and Videos.
Arts Council England; Garfield Weston Foundation; John Lyon's Charity; City Bridge Foundation; Community Fund and Wandsworth Council	ActionSpace: for artists with Learning Disabilities	Organisation Website	UK	Creative Hub, Supported Studio and Artist Development Agency working with artists with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Independence through Art - actionspace. Develop a model for an accessible life skills course, using visual arts activities as a tool for learning through doing.

Arts Council England; Arts Council of Wales; Garfield Weston Foundation; Joseph Rowntree Foundation; Heritage Fund; Buckinghamshire New University; Schuh	Shape Arts	Organisation Website	UK	Improving access to culture by providing opportunities for creatives with disabilities, training cultural institutions to be more accessible and inclusive, and by running participatory arts and development programmes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Podcast. Discussions around arts, heritage and creativity of all kinds from a barriers-facing perspective, and hearing from activists and cultural workers about the things that matter to them
Arts Council England	Mind The Gap	Organisation Website	UK	Premier learning disability performance and arts company, breaking barriers and celebrating diversity for artists with learning disabilities and autism.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Project Depository. List of all past initiatives led by the organisation centring artists with disabilities.
Arts Council England	Attitude is everything -improving access together	Organisation Website	UK	Connect people with disabilities with music and live event industries valuing people with disabilities as audience and as artists.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ State of Access Report. Examining the barriers faced by Deaf people and people with disabilities in general when trying to book tickets for live music events.
Creative Scotland	Birds of Paradise Theatre Company	Organisation Website	UK	Touring theatre company employing actors with and without disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ House Lights Up! Researching Relaxed performances for Neurodivergent Audiences in Scotland. Report to better understand how to remove barriers in cultural spaces
Arts Council England; Liverpool City Council	Dada- Celebrating disability and Deaf arts - Creating Art, Challenging Attitudes, Changing Lives	Organisation Website	UK	International reach and impact carrying out events supporting artists with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resources. Outputs available by request.

Arts Council of Wales; Welsh Government; Wales Millennium Centre; Ethical Management Member; Disability Confident	Hijinx	Organisation Website	UK	Improving participation in theatre and film and art of people with learning disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research outputs. Findings on how screen content could be made in an authentically inclusive way for actors with a learning disability with their input from the outset.
Arts Council England; Heritage Fund; Community Fund; Paul Hamlyn Foundation; Wandsworth Borough; the Victoria Wood Foundation and individual donors	Oily Cart	Organisation Website	UK	Creating accessible shows that connect young people, and their families with sensory theatre initiative tailored to neurodiverse children.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sensory Theatre -How to Make Interactive, Inclusive, Immersive Theatre for Diverse Audiences. An accessible step-by-step guide to creating theatre for inclusive audiences.
National Lottery; Arts Council England	Oska Bright Film Festival	Organisation Website	UK	World's leading festival for films made by or featuring people with learning disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Archive. Past festival programming available on the website.
Arts Council England	Ramps on the Moon	Organisation Website	UK	Collaborative consortium which aims to enrich the stories by elevating the presences of Deaf and people with disabilities on and off stage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resources and Videos. Masterclasses on integrating access into a show or organisation.
Arts Council England	StageTEXT	Organisation Website	UK	Aim to make the arts welcoming and accessible by using the latest technology to set the highest standards in access.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resources ▪ Stagetext. Best Practice Checklist, Caption and subtitles guides and more.

Several organisations, including Arts Council England and the National Lottery Community Fund	Together! 2012 CIC- Disability Art, Culture & Human Rights	Organisation Website	UK	Creating a Paralympic cultural Legacy in London by contributing to an international centre of excellence for Disability Arts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource list. Includes definitions, guides on accessibility, documentations for filmmakers, art organisations, and more.
Arts Council England	VocalEyes	Organisation Website	UK	Opportunities of blind and visually impaired people to experience and enjoy art and heritage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Audience Surveys. List of surveys providing a greater understanding of the place, possibilities and barriers for people with disabilities within the arts.
UK Government; Arts Council England	Without Walls	Organisation Website	UK	Promotion of good practices and inclusivity of Deaf and audiences and artists with disabilities amongst festivals and events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Outdoor Arts Festival Events: Access Guide. Guide to promote good practice amongst festivals and events that are involved in the network.
Arts Council England; Bloomberg Philantropies	Graeae	Organisation Website	UK	Mission to create theatrical excellence through the vision and practice of artists with various disabilities or Deaf or neurodivergent artists to combat societal expectations of people with disabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ List of current and past shows. They include usually accessible measures such as British Sign Language interpretation and captions, creative use of audio description, and are either led/performed by artists with disabilities.
Arts Council England; Arts Council of Wales; Paul Hamlyn Foundation;	Unlimited	Organisation Website	UK	Arts commissioning body that supports, funds and promotes new work by artists with disabilities for UK and international audiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ List of Resources. Resources for artists, creatives, producers and the sector to share best practice, insights, toolkits and more.
Arts Council England; Without Walls	Daryl and Co.	Organisation Website	UK	Children's theatre company led by people with disabilities to make theatre accessible to young audiences and their families.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Online Access and Inclusion Training for Arts Professionals. Videos and Resources Training Material for cultural organisations and their teams to enhance their understanding of access and inclusion.

DANCING

